

Analyzing Repetitive DNA Involved in Tissue Regeneration in Echinoderms

Mabe, Gerald Branden

University of North Carolina at Charlotte

BACKGROUND

- Humans have limited regenerative properties. However, echinoderms are related to humans and can undergo whole body regeneration (WBR) when exposed to trauma (Mashanov *et al.*, 2012).
- Sclerodactyla briareus* (a sea cucumber) and *Ophioderma brevispina* (a brittle star) have great regenerative potential, but their genome assemblies are fragmented and hard to work with, partly due to repetitive elements (Mashanov *et al.*, 2014).
- Repetitive elements are sequences of nucleotides that repeat themselves throughout the genome (Burns, 2020).
- They have been implicated to play a role in tissue regeneration in echinoderms, but the precise molecular mechanisms are still unknown (Mashanov *et al.*, 2012).
- Asterias rubens* (a common starfish) has a high-quality genome that can be used to examine the role of repetitive elements in tissue regeneration, but there is a lack of a consistent classification system to understand repetitive elements.
- To successfully complete our analyses on the potential effects of repetitive elements on regeneration, we proposed an improved system of repetitive element classification.
- We are also working on new methodologies to estimate repeat copy numbers using the *A. rubens* genome and the improved classification system.

OBJECTIVE

- Create an improved classification system for repetitive elements that is consistent throughout the literature and aids in comparative genomics of echinoderms.

METHODS

- A widespread bibliographical review was conducted on available classification systems for repetitive elements.
- One specific system devised by Wicker *et al.* (2007) was used as a baseline.
- We proposed an improved classification system for repetitive elements that is like current biological classification and could encompass all types of repetitive elements.

We present an improved classification system for repetitive DNA elements that is more comprehensive than previous versions and will facilitate genome comparisons and greater insights into phylogeny and function.

Table 1. Ranking: Good. Randomly-selected examples of repetitive elements in the *Asterias rubens* genome organized according to RepeatMasker by Smit *et al.* (2020).

Sequence ID	Start position (bp)	End position (bp)	Classification
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	142549	142994	LINE/Dong-R4
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143037	143127	Unknown
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143318	143456	LINE/L2

Table 2. Ranking: Better. Randomly-selected examples of repetitive elements in the *Asterias rubens* genome organized according to Wicker *et al.* (2007).

Sequence ID	Start (bp)	End (bp)	Class	Sub-class	Order	Super-family	Family	Sub-family	Insertion	Structural Description
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	142549	142994	Retro-transposons	N/A	LINEs	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143037	143127	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143318	143456	Retro-transposons	N/A	LINEs	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	LINE2

Table 3. Ranking: Best. Randomly-selected examples of repetitive elements in the *Asterias rubens* genome organized according to the improved classification system proposed herein.

Sequence ID	Start	End	Phylum	Class	Sub-class	Order	Super-family	Family	Sub-family	Type	Sub-type
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	142549	142994	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposons	Unknown	LINEs	?	?	?
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143037	143127	Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143318	143456	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposons	Unknown	LINEs	Unknown	LINE2	?

RESULTS

Our system leverages on the accepted classification system for transposable elements and creates a framework in which different types of repetitive DNA elements can be analyzed. Most notably, our system:

- Detaches the biological meaning from the hierarchical levels of classification so that the biological meaning is attached to the names of each group only.
- Includes a new upper level, Phylum, that divides transposons and non-transposons, allowing all repetitive elements to be organized within the same overall framework.
- Adds clarity to the classification of LINEs. Wicker *et al.* (2007) classifies LINEs as Orders and Non-LTR retrotransposons as Subclasses. We propose that Non-LTR retrotransposons be classified as Orders and LINEs classified as a Family. This is more intuitive, as Wicker *et al.* (2007) classifies LTR retrotransposons as an Order, not a Subclass of repetitive elements.
- Alters the classification for "Class" to increase clarity and simplicity. Class 1 elements refer to DNA transposons. Class 2 elements refer to retrotransposons. If a repetitive element is neither, such as repetitive RNA, the classification is simply N/A.
- Adds clear formatting rules to improve consistency. Each label after "Order" should be italicized, keeping in accordance with current biological classification systems.
- Uses "Unknown" when more specific labels have been determined but preceding levels of classification have not.

DISCUSSION

- The improved classification system will aid in our understanding of repetitive elements and their evolution.
- Previous efforts to devise methodologies to quantify repeats in *de novo* genome assemblies failed partially due to our inability to organize repetitive elements in distinctive categories and efficiently addressed their different biological characteristics.
- We hope that the improved classification system here will facilitate downstream analysis and aid us while we develop new methodologies to analyze repetitive DNA across different non-model organisms.

CONCLUSION

- Our improved classification system for repetitive DNA elements provides an important framework that will aid in all downstream analyses of repetitive elements, helping elucidate their role in tissue regeneration in echinoderms.

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